

IF YOU TEST NEGATIVE FOR COVID-19...

A negative test result means you probably were not infected with COVID-19 at the time of testing. Take these steps to protect yourself:

Get vaccinated

- Once you are fully vaccinated, you can start doing some things that you had stopped

Wear a mask when inside in public

- Cover your nose, mouth, and chin snugly
- Wear masks at home if someone in your household has COVID-19

Stay 6 feet away from others

- **Inside your home:** Wear a mask and try to stay 6 feet from anyone who is sick.
- **Outside your home:** Keep a 6-foot distance between yourself and others

Wash your hands often

- Wash with soap and water for at least 20 seconds

It's important to wash:

- Before eating or preparing food
- Before touching your face
- After using the bathroom
- After leaving a public place
- After blowing your nose, coughing, or sneezing
- After handling your mask
- After changing a diaper
- After caring for someone sick
- After touching animals or pets

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60%

- If soap and water are not available, use a hand sanitizer that has at least 60% alcohol.
- Do not touch your eyes, nose, and mouth with unwashed hands

Cover coughs and sneezes

- **If you are wearing a mask:** you can cough or sneeze into your mask. Put on a new, clean mask as soon as possible and wash your hands

- **If you are not wearing a mask:** use a tissue or the inside of your elbow to cover your mouth and nose when you cough or sneeze.

Avoid crowds and poorly ventilated spaces

- Crowded places like restaurants, bars, gyms, or movie theaters put you at higher risk
- Avoid areas that do not have good air flow
- Open windows and doors